

Fig. S1. Neighbor-Joining tree of the 1,062 COI sequences of the present study encompassing 37 species.

BOLD TaxonID Tree

Title : Tree Result - DS-BIFCOPY (1062 records selected)
Date : 07-Nov-2023
Data Type : Nucleotide
Distance Model : Kimura 2 Parameter
Marker : COI-5P
Colourization : [blue]=Stop Codons [red]=Contamination or misidentification

Label : Sample ID
Label : Taxon
Label : Barcode Cluster (BIN)

Sequence Count : 1060
Species count : 37
Genus count : 15
Family count : 6
Unidentified : 51

BIN Count : 90

2 %

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Fig. S2. (left) Extended Bayesian Skyline Plots representing the variation of the median effective population size through time based on mitogenomes and COI data (right) and Bayesian Skyline Plot based on COI data only (left).

Fig. S3. Extended Bayesian Skyline Plots representing the variation of the median effective population size through time based on mitogenomes and COI data for MOTU with multiple mitogenomes.

Fig. S4. Cross-validation of the hABC of mode (top), mean (middle) and median (bottom) with MOTUs mutation rates corresponding to the product of generation time and a substitution rate of 1.2×10^{-8} % per year (left); 2.4×10^{-8} % per year (middle); and 7.2×10^{-8} % per year (right). Simulated data calculated using Fastsimcol for number of MOTUs with constant N_e through time (ζ) observed based on the present data set. Inferred data correspond to hABC estimates based on simulated data.

Fig. S5. Cross validation of the hABC method performed on datasets of 5000 simulated loci. Three-point estimates of the posterior distribution are shown: mode (top), mean (middle) and median (bottom). x-axis corresponds to the simulated number of MOTUs with constant N_e , y-axis correspond to the hABC estimates.

Table S1. List of the 1,078 samples analyzed in the present study including systematic (Family, Genus, Species), sample ID (BOLD), GenBank accession numbers for COI and Complete Mitochondrial Genomes (CMG), MOTU numbers assigned with BOLD, sPTP, mPTP, sGMYC, mGMYC and ABGD and majority-rule consensus, Locality (Country, State.Province, Region, Sector, Exact.Site, Latitude, Longitude,) and corresponding paleoriver.

Table S2. Diversity indices used for hABC analyses. Number of specimen (N), total number of sites (No.sites), number of segregating sites (s), nucleotidic diversity (π); Theta S computed by site (Theta S), Tajima's D and generation time in years (T). Prior distributions are as follow: all Ne are extracted from a Uniform prior bounded between 50 ÷ 2000000; Time of demographic change τ is extracted from a Uniform prior bounded between 10 and 3000000. The number of MOTUs with constant Ne through time (ζ) is extracted from a discrete Uniform prior bounded between 1 and 17.

MOTUs	Morphological species	N	No. sites	s	π ($\times 10^{-4}$)	Theta S	Tajima's D	T
MOTU1	<i>Anabas testidineus</i>	36	651	8	47.79	2.943	0.258	0.6
MOTU10	<i>Barbodes binotatus</i>	14	651	7	24.14	2.201	-1.0567	3.3
MOTU19	<i>Monopterus javanensis</i>	34	651	10	36.17	2.446	-0.137	8.3
MOTU2	<i>Barbodes binotatus</i>	193	651	51	77.38	10.621	-1.638	3.3
MOTU26	<i>Parachela hypophthalmus</i>	40	651	9	10.80	2.116	-1.987	2.3
MOTU27	<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>	26	651	8	27.18	2.096	-0.491	1.5
MOTU28	<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>	43	641	16	41.18	3.698	-0.912	1.5
MOTU34	<i>Channa striata</i>	135	651	38	97.02	6.936	-0.269	2
MOTU36	<i>Chitala borneesis</i>	9	651	8	47.79	2.944	0.258	4.5
MOTU45	<i>Hampala macrolepidota</i>	17	612	11	44.45	3.254	-0.608	2.4
MOTU5	<i>Barbodes binotatus</i>	14	651	28	84.74	8.805	-1.596	3.3
MOTU6	<i>Barbodes binotatus</i>	12	651	4	16.52	1.325	-0.661	3.3
MOTU84	<i>Trigonopoma pauciperforatum</i>	11	651	6	46.64	2.390	1.098	1.2
MOTU86	<i>Trigonopoma pauciperforatum</i>	12	651	8	44.22	2.649	0.346	1.2
MOTU88	<i>Trigonopoma pauciperforatum</i>	8	651	11	44.99	4.242	-1.547	1.2
MOTU94	<i>Trigonopoma pauciperforatum</i>	32	651	24	87.95	5.959	-0.137	1.2
MOTU95	<i>Trigonopoma pauciperforatum</i>	47	651	16	72.30	3.849	0.703	1.2

Table S3. Posterior estimates of the number of MOTU with constant Ne through time (ζ).

Parameter	2.5 %	Median	Mode	97.5 %	Priors	Model
ζ	2	12	16	16	Uniform: 1-17	clock rate 1
ζ	2	11	16	16	Uniform: 1-17	clock rate 2
ζ	1	8	16	16	Uniform: 1-17	clock rate 3